

Programmable Integrated Photonics: State of the Art and Future Trends

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Abstract: Here we review past, present and future work in the next photonic ICs generation aiming the integration of multi-functional software-defined systems for signal processing operations.

OCIS codes: (130.0130) Integrated optics; (070.1170) Analog optical signal processing.

1. Introduction

Since the first integration of photonic circuits, scientists have tried to increase the versatility and flexibility of their components. This is commonly achieved by changing the effective index properties of the waveguides through the application of different electro-optical, thermo-optical, electro-mechanical or electro-magnetic effects. The controlled alteration of the phase and absorption of light has led to the design of integrated modulators, tunable filters, tunable splitters, optical switches and flexible beamforming networks to cite a few examples. The notion of reconfigurable photonic components has evolved to more complex photonic integrated circuits (PICs), where the versatility is conferred to the whole system. By software programming each subsystem after fabrication, multiple functionalities are targeted with a single hardware platform, [1]. Doing so will radically enable cost-effective photonic-driven solutions to the market, and will potentially create the opportunity for a new field to be explored in terms of generic photonic hardware and software development opportunities.

Programmable Integrated Photonics can be divided into: Multipurpose devices and reconfigurable subsystems. While the latter can be reconfigured to increase the performance of a certain application (e.g. filter tunability/reconfigurability) the former focuses on a wider range of applications. Here, we will provide a deep analysis and overview of the state of the art of this field.

2. Looking for the most versatile system architecture:

The great promise of versatile integrated optics lies in integrating the optimum number of components to perform the greatest number of functionalities with a common/shared hardware. In Fig.1 (a), we can see an example of an integrated system that incorporates an array of electro/optic and opto/electronic converters, several optical sources and a reconfigurable optical core. These processing architectures allow multiple photonic processing functionalities as well as microwave / millimeter wave operations, [2]. Fig. 1 (b) illustrates an example of different design layers.

Fig1. (a) Schematic of a generic-purpose photonic processor architecture covering RF-photonics assisted operations and photonic operations. (b) Design tiers distribution.

3. Waveguide meshes

A very versatile optical processing engine is required to implement the core of these architectures. The purpose of this element is two-fold. It needs first, to provide a reconfigurable/dynamic interconnection scheme between all the subsystems. Secondly, it should support the main optical signal processing operations. These tasks can be achieved by means of High Performance Blocks (see Fig. 1 (a)), specifically designed to perform a single functionality (e.g. high-selectivity narrowband filtering) or/and by waveguide mesh arrangements [3,4]. These arrangements are massive interconnections of waveguide pairs coupled by a 2x2 beamsplitting elements (mainly a balanced Mach-Zehnder Interferometers with a phase modulator on each arm), describing closed unity cells. Conventional PICs are then discretized into these Tunable Basic Units (TBUs) to define the light path geometries and design parameters of the synthesized/programmed circuits.

Fig. 2 illustrates the first three experimental examples in the field specifying their labelled layout details and fabrication photograph: (by chronological order): Fig. 2(a) shows the programmable optical chip architecture reported by Zhuang and co-workers in silicon nitride. Next, we reported the results of a waveguide mesh composed of 7 hexagonal cells (30 thermally-tuned TBUs) fabricated in silicon on insulator, (for more details on fabrication and testing see [3]). Finally, we recently designed a mesh based on thermally-tuned 40 TBUs which is shown in Fig. 2(c). In this case, we re-designed the shape of the TBU to achieve a more compact layout and increase the component integration density. This chip has been fabricated in a Multi-Project Wafer run at a fabrication platform at the Centro Nacional de Microelectrónica (CNM-VLC platform), and is currently under test.

Despite the simplicity of the layouts depicted in Fig.2, even the 7-cell structure is capable of implementing over 100 different circuits for optical filtering applications (basic MZI, FIR transversal filters, basic tunable ring cavities and IIR filters, as well as compound structures such as CROWs and SCISSORS), true time delay lines and optical coherent interferometry, [4].

The current and future research in the field is focused on alternative tuning mechanisms to reduce the overall power consumption and footprints, TBU geometries and loss optimization and the development of software to drive and control the reconfigurable subsystems.

Fig.2. Chip picture and fabricated layout for different waveguide meshes: (a) Square topology in SiN [3], (b) Hexagonal topology in Silicon [4], (c) Hexagonal topology in SiN with modified TBU scheme., BUL: Basic Unit Length of the Tunable Basic Unit (defined in [4]).

4 References

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